

What is Galaxy?

- An open platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational biomedical research
- Toolshed with 1,000s of tools ready to run
- Terabytes of the latest, curated reference data
- Full featured workflow functionality
- Graphical interface for handling >1,000 samples
- Run Jupyter, RStudio, & Interactive Visualizations
- Extensive training tutorials and infrastructure
- Large international community of users and developers

All of this can be used on free public high performance infrastructure... or your institutional cluster... or the cloud... or your laptop... or a Raspberry Pi!

